

Use of Multimedia Resources for Self-regulated Learning by Undergraduate Students of the Department of Library and Information Science, Bayero University Kano

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Abstract

This study investigated the use of multimedia resources for self-regulated learning by the undergraduate students of the department of library and information science, Bayero University, Kano. The researchers used a survey research design and employed convenient sampling to select 256 respondents out of a population of 601 undergraduate students. A questionnaire was used to collect data, and the results were analyzed using descriptive statistics and simple linear regression. The findings revealed that the undergraduate library and information science students used significantly multimedia resources (weighted mean = 2.84), and potentially self-regulated their learning curve (weighted mean = 3.0), which resulted in significant acquisition of knowledge and fast learning. The linear regression results indicated that the use of multimedia resources statistically significantly predicted the self-regulated learning of undergraduate students of library and information sciences ($F(1, 254) = 60.840$; $R^2 = .190$; $\beta = .409$, $p < .001$), which implies that 19.0% change in self-regulated learning of the studies students was explained by their use of multimedia resources for educational purposes. The study concluded that students in tertiary institutions Bayero University Kano have the propensity to self-regulate their learning activities with the support of multimedia resources. The provision of Internet service, Wireless Access Points and subscription to multimedia resources online database by Nigerian university libraries are recommended.

Keywords: *Multimedia, Self-regulated Learning, Education, Library and Information Science*

Introduction

Self-regulated learning (SRL) is recognized as an essential skill for academic success and lifelong learning. It involves students actively managing their own learning through processes like goal-setting, employing strategies, self-monitoring, and self-evaluation. Technology, including multimedia resources, has the potential to support the development of these self-regulatory abilities. However, limited research has been conducted on the effectiveness of multimedia in enhancing SRL, especially in the undergraduate population.

The acquisition of SRL abilities is crucial for tertiary-level academic achievement. Transitioning from secondary school to higher education can pose challenges in fostering independent learning and self-directedness. SRL encompasses learners' ability to oversee their own learning through metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral mechanisms such as goal setting, progress monitoring, seeking assistance, and self-reflection. Proficient SRL skills have been linked to higher academic achievements and persistence in studies at the postsecondary level, highlighting the importance of developing SRL when students enter higher education environments characterized by increased academic rigor and self-directed learning.

Multimedia resources capture learners' attention and maintain their interest (Ma & She, 2023). They make the learning process more interactive and enjoyable, stimulating active participation and engagement. This increased engagement leads to better knowledge retention and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Different individuals have different learning preferences, such as visual, auditory, or kinesthetic learning. Multimedia resources cater to these varied modalities by presenting information through various formats. (Taranto & Buchanan, 2020; Ma & She, 2023; Lismarini, 2019) For instance, visual learners benefit from images and videos, while auditory learners benefit from audio recordings or podcasts. By accommodating diverse learning styles, multimedia resources ensure that learners can access information in a way that suits them best.

Snowden and Hardy (2013) posited that multimedia resources often present information from multiple perspectives, encouraging learners to think critically, evaluate different viewpoints, and develop analytical skills. By presenting real-life examples, case studies, and interactive scenarios, multimedia resources foster a deeper understanding of complex concepts and encourage learners to apply their knowledge in practical situations. (Anisa et al., 2020).

Access to up-to-date information: With the rapid evolution of technology and information, multimedia resources provide access to the latest research, data, and developments in various fields. Online databases, digital libraries, and multimedia platforms offer a vast array of resources that can be easily updated and accessed by learners and researchers. This ensures that users have access to the most recent and relevant information for their studies or research. It is also reported by Eastman and Swift (2002), Li and Li, (2022), and Baskaran et al., (2014) multimedia resources can enable collaborative learning by incorporating features like discussion forums, chat rooms, and video conferencing tools. These resources encourage learners to interact with peers, exchange ideas, and work together on projects. Collaborative learning enhances communication skills, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities, which are essential in academic and professional settings.

As acknowledged by Chriki et al. (2020), multimedia resources have the advantage of being easily accessible anytime and anywhere, regardless of geographical location. This accessibility allows learners and researchers to access information, courses, and research materials remotely. It promotes lifelong learning and enables individuals from different parts of the world to benefit from educational resources and research findings.

Recent empirical research has provided confirmation that the incorporation of multimedia in educational settings has a positive impact on learning outcomes and the development of skills. According to Jenő et al. (2019), engineering students experienced enhanced analytical skills through the utilisation of self-regulated learning (SRL) with the aid of video modules. According to Adnan and Anwar (2020), teacher trainees acquired technological competencies by engaging in self-paced multimedia courses. This highlights the necessity for students in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS) to effectively utilise the educational opportunities presented by multimedia for self-directed learning.

Nevertheless, there is a scarcity of studies focusing on the particular use of multimedia for self-regulated learning (SRL) among students in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS), particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. The implementation of multimedia technologies in LIS programmes necessitates a deeper understanding of the practical usage practises, as highlighted by Baro and Eze (2019). The examination of how students discover, engage with,

and utilise multimedia materials can provide valuable insights for educators seeking to effectively utilise these resources to promote self-directed learning.

The use of multimedia technologies in LIS education can enhance its effectiveness in meeting the demands of the digital era. However, it is imperative that students possess a comprehensive understanding of how to engage with these platforms from a self-regulated learning (SRL) perspective.

Research Questions

1. What are the types of multimedia resources used for self-regulated learning by the undergraduate students of the department of library and information science in Bayero University, Kano?
2. To what extent do undergraduate students of the department of library and information science, Bayero University Kano use multimedia resources for self-regulated learning?

Hypothesis

H₀: Use of multimedia resources has no significant influence on self-regulated Learning of undergraduate students of the department of Library and Information Science, Bayero University, Kano

Research Methodology

This study used survey research design. The population of the study consisted of six hundred and one (601) undergraduate students in Department of Library and Information sciences of Bayero University, Kano as the time of the study. 256 sample size was determined through Raosoft Web-based Sample Size Calculator. Convenience sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study, which was done during lecture period as points of meeting. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. 256 copies of the questionnaires were administered, successfully collected and found valid, reliable and usable for analysis. The data were analysed with descriptive statistics of mean score and standard deviation as well as inferential statistics of simple linear regression in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Two: Table 1: Type of multimedia resources used for self-regulated learning

SNO	Types of Multimedia Resources used by students	\bar{X}	Std.
1.	I use multimedia such as YouTube site to access interrelated educational video contents to support my self-regulated learning	3.02	.986
2.	I use search engines such as Google, Bing, Yahoo search engines to identify and locate interactive information contents to enhance my self-regulated learning	3.20	.973
3.	I use online dictionaries such as Wikipedia and online encyclopaedia with links of texts, audio, video, graphics, images to quickly locate other related concepts, products and services or documents to facilitate my self-regulated learning	2.79	.716
4.	I use social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Twitter to access an interactive educational information for self-regulated learning	2.88	.845
5.	I use Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) such as lynda.com, Coursera, to acquire skills and knowledge to facilitate my educational career through their hyperlinks for self-regulated learning	2.32	.970
Weighted Mean		2.84	

Source: Fieldwork, 2021; **Key:** Strongly disagree (SD) Disagree (D), Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA)

Table 1 showcases the types of multimedia resources that were used by Library and Information Science Undergraduate Students (LISUS) for self-regulated learning. According to the data presented, the LISUS strongly agreed that they used Public Search Engines e.g. Google, Bing, Yahoo to identify and locate interactive information contents for self-regulated learning ($\bar{x} = 3.20$, Std. = .973). Majority of them also strongly agreed that they used web-based multimedia e.g. YouTube site to access interrelated educational video contents to support their self-regulated learning ($\bar{x} = 3.02$, Std. = .986). They agreed that they used social media e.g., Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Twitter to access an interactive educational information for self-regulated learning ($\bar{x} = 2.88$, Std. = .845).

Many agreed that they used Online Dictionaries e.g. Wikipedia and online encyclopaedia with links of texts, audio, video, graphics, images to quickly locate

other related concepts, products and services or documents to enhance self-regulated learning ($\bar{x} = 2.79$, Std. = .716). However, they LISUS disagreed that they used CD/DVD/Blu-ray Interactive Course contents to facilitate their learning ($\bar{x} = 2.49$, Std. = .912), and also disagreed that they used Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) e.g., lynda.com, Coursera, etc. to acquire skills and knowledge to facilitate their educational career through their hyperlinks ($\bar{x} = 2.32$, Std. = .970).

Two: Table 2: Extent of Use of multimedia resources for self-regulated learning by undergraduate students

SN	Extent of use of multimedia resources for self-regulated learning	\bar{X}	Std.
1.	My SRL learning with multimedia resources helped me acquire to more knowledge	3.11	.885
2.	Learning is easier for me when I set goals and guide myself in learning with multimedia resources	2.89	.811
3.	I use most of my time in SRL with multimedia resources	3.33	.955
4.	With multimedia resources at my disposal, I need little or no guidance in learning	3.09	.982
5.	I develop high sense of consistent learning with multimedia resources	2.92	.758
6.	Flexibility in my learning effort is due to multimedia resources	2.92	.790
7.	Self-regulated learning with multimedia resources gives me unwavering support in my learning	2.98	.858

Weighted mean

3.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2021; **Key:** *Strongly disagree (SD) Disagree (D), Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA)*

The table 2 displays the responses of library and information science undergraduate students regarding the efficacy of using multimedia on self-regulated learning. The responses showed that they strongly agreed that self-regulating their learning with multimedia resources allowed them to gain more knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.33$, Std. = .955). The respondents strongly agreed that they learnt faster when they personally regulate their learning processes aided by multimedia resources ($\bar{x} = 3.11$, Std. = .885). The respondent equally strongly agreed that with multimedia resources at their disposal, they needed little or no guidance in learning ($\bar{x} = 3.09$, Std. = .982).

The respondents also agreed that self-regulated learning with multimedia gives them unwavering support in their learning ($\bar{x} = 2.98$, Std. = .858). The respondents more so agreed that they developed high sense of consistent learning with multimedia resources ($\bar{x} = 2.92$, Std. = .758). Based on the data, the respondents agreed that flexibility in their learning effort was due to multimedia resources used ($\bar{x} = 2.92$, Std. = .790), and agreed that learning was easier for them when they set goals and guided themselves in learning with multimedia resources ($\bar{x} = 2.89$, Std. = .811).

Looking closer at the means scores students expressed strongest agreement with the idea that use of multimedia enables acquisition of more knowledge ($\bar{X}=3.11$) and helps them use time effectively for self-regulated learning ($\bar{X}=3.33$). They were comparatively less convinced that multimedia provides unwavering support ($\bar{X}=2.98$) or reduces the need for instructor guidance ($\bar{X}=3.09$), with these items showing lower means.

The finding indicates that the library and information science students' perceiving multimedia as somewhat valuable in supporting self-direction, but still desiring guidance and scaffolding. The moderate standard deviations (.758 to .982) indicate a fair degree of variation in student perspectives, rather than a strong consensus. This implies that the students agree to a moderate extent that multimedia facilitates self-regulated learning, but they do not see it as a full replacement for instructor support and continue to seek guidance.

Analysis of Hypothesis

Table 3: Influence of multimedia use on SRL of LISUS BUK

Adjusted R Square	Df	F	β	t	Sig.
.190	1	60.840	1.915	13.005	.001
	254		.409	7.800	

Table 3 presents the data about the influence of multimedia resources on the self-regulated learning of library and information science undergraduate students in Bayero University, Kano. By this result the null hypothesis which stated the use of multimedia resources has no significant influence on SRL of library and information science undergraduate students of Bayero University Kano was rejected. This can be re-stated that there is a statistical evidence to assert that multimedia resources have a positive influence on the self regulated learning of

undergraduate students of Bayero University Kano as seen by the results of $F(1, 256) = 60.840, p = .001$). Really.

In addition, using the regression equation model ($Y = a + b * x$) where $a = 1.916$ is the constant or intercept and $b = .409$ is the slope or rise of the use of multimedia for self-regulated learning. It can be modelled as $Y = 1.916 + .409 * X$ where the X is the use of multimedia. In other words, the adjusted R square indicates that 19.0% variation or successes in self-regulated learning by LISUS is explained by the use of multimedia resources, which implies that use of multimedia resources actually predicted self-regulated learning.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that library and information science undergraduate students use multimedia resources such as text, audio, images, video, animation, public search engines especially Google, Public Search Engines; Online Dictionaries & encyclopaedias with links of text audio, video, graphics images to quickly locate other related concepts, products, and services or documents; social media (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Twitter) all to enhance self regulated learning.

This corroborates with Mohammed, 2021 and Pavithra, Athilingam and Prakash, 2018 who all agreed that the multimedia earlier mentioned were used by students for SRL. However, the students studied do not use Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCS) e.g., coursera, edX, Lynda.com; CD/DVD/Blu-ray for self-regulated learning. The reason for not using the aforementioned multimedia could be attributed to unfamiliarity, lack of awareness or lack of proficiency with such technologies.

The findings of the study also showed that the use of multimedia resources by the students studied was effective for self- regulated learning. Multimedia resources had a positive influence on the SRL of the students. Multimedia resources facilitate gaining of more knowledge; easier learning; judicious use of time in learning; little guidance in learning; flexibility in learning and; supportive learning of the students. This is as a result of the majority of the students who responded positively as shown in table 2.

This finding corroborates the statement of Alvi et. al (2016) that asserted that self-regulated learning is critical to enable successes among students from an early age

through all stages of learning. The finding is also supported by Bulu and Pedersen (2012) who reported that self-regulated learning is an important educational construct that has been shown to be effective for students as they learn and study various subjects. This is important because it not only equips student to rely on class room teachings but to go a step further in finding other multimedia tools and channels to compliment and their yearnings for knowledge and skill seeking activities. The implication is that students will become independent and life-long learners as they can rely on themselves to learn better in the technologically driven world that we find ourselves.

Conclusion

The study examined the use of multimedia resources for self-regulated learning among undergraduate students of Library and Information Science students in Bayero University Kano, Nigeria. Findings showed that multimedia resources are essential for better educational pursuit through which academic excellence can be achieved by students.

It can also be suggested that self-regulated learning can extensively broaden the knowledge and skills of students as they adopt student-centric approach to learning, particularly by the use of multimedia resources. Finally, the relationship between use of multimedia resources and self-regulated learning is a manifestation of students' efforts in exploiting the various benefits of such resources as reliable media for enhancing their learning activities.

Recommendations

The Department of Library and Information Science, Bayero University Kano, as well as other Library Schools should deploy Information and Communication Technology infrastructure in teaching library students on how create, repackage, preserve and disseminate to bolster the efforts of students in accessing and using multimedia resources for faster knowledge attainment, skills acquisition and academic excellence.

By establishing that predictive relationship exists between the use of multimedia resources and self-regulated learning among students, libraries in academic institutions should acquire and disseminate multimedia resources in various disciplines to augment class teaching activities and life-long learning.

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